

Disease resistance

Hybrid lines from two rice crosses, originally intended for other purposes, are being studied as possible new sources of resistance to grassy stunt virus disease. The only source of resistance to grassy stunt known so far is IRRI Acc. 101508 of *Oryza nivara*. Examining an infected field above (left to right) are IRRI scientists S. H. Ou, plant pathology; G. S. Khush, plant breeding; and K. C. Ling, plant pathology.

Two possible new sources of resistance to grassy stunt virus disease of rice

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In 1973, a very severe outbreak of brown planthoppers and a grassy stunt virus disease of rice occurred in Laguna province, Philippines, including the IRRI farm. Several hybrid lines from two crosses exhibited high levels of resistance to both under field conditions. The two crosses are IR9560 (IR8³//IR8/Carreon//IR8/Tetep), which was intended to incorporate blast resistance from different sources, and IR4497 (IR24//Zenith/Malagkit Sungsong), which was made to increase the spectrum of resistance to bacterial blight. Several single plants from these crosses were selected and grown separately in pots in the greenhouse. They were artificially inoculated with grassy stunt virus at 2 weeks after sowing in the F₄ generation. Most selections were highly resistant to the disease. The percentage of infection ranged from 0 to 12 percent

for IR9560 lines and from 2 to 9 percent for IR4497 lines. Since only one source of resistance to grassy stunt is known so far, IRRI Acc. 101508 of *Oryza nivara*, these new sources may be valuable alternate sources in breeding for grassy stunt resistance. All parents of the two crosses are susceptible to grassy stunt. The resistance genes involved in these lines are being investigated.

Pathogenic variability of *Xanthomonas oryzae*

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During the 1975 wet season, IR30, which carries the dominant gene for bacterial blight resistance, was found susceptible in Iloilo and Davao provinces, Philippines. Pathogenicity studies indicated that the isolates of *X. oryzae* from these areas attacked IR20 and IR30 in a manner similar to that of the Isabela strain.

However, varieties that carried a recessive gene for resistance were not overcome by these isolates in the greenhouse.

A test of 83 isolates on IR8 (with no resistance gene), IR20 (carrying *Xa* 4, a dominant gene for resistance), and IR1545 (carrying *xa* 5, a recessive gene for resistance) suggested distinct differential interactions. At least four pathogenic groups of the isolates were observed. It is evident that the pathogenic variability of *X. oryzae* differed not only in virulence but also in pathogenicity. Current efforts are underway to evaluate varieties that will differentiate the Philippine isolates into pathogenic races.

Blast resistance in cold-tolerant boro rice of Uttar Pradesh

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The boro crop of rice is grown in the eastern districts of Uttar Pradesh state near rivers, lakes, and large ponds. Nurseries are sown in November and the crop is harvested around the end of April. During early growth, the crop faces cool temperatures in December and January (as low as 2°C with a monthly av. min. temp. of 10°C). To our knowledge, this rice has not been systematically collected. Therefore the present collection was started in 1972. After purification, 90 distinct types were isolated. The rices were screened against blast disease at Rice Research Station Majhera (29.28°N, 79.32°E and 650 msl), a blast-endemic area, in 1974 and 1975. The material was grown in rod-rows and scored for disease reaction after 1½ months following the method of S. H. Ou (1965). Final grading of the entries was based on highest score value recorded in both years. No entry proved highly resistant (see table). Only 5.6 percent were resistant and 5.6 percent were moderately resistant. Almost 89 percent were in the susceptible classes (88.8%).

The five resistant rices are UPRB-7, UPRB-8, UPRB-31, UPRB-32, and UPRB-33. UPRB-8 has intermediate height and the others are tall. UPRB-7,

Reaction of boro collections to blast disease. G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, U. P., India.

Reaction	Collections	
	(no.)	(% of total)
Highly resistant	0	0.0
Resistant	5	5.6
Mod. resistant	5	5.6
Mod. susceptible	4	4.5
Susceptible	7	7.8
Very susceptible	14	15.6
Highly susceptible	55	60.9

8, and 31 have white kernels and UPRB-32 and 33 have red kernels. UPRB-8 and UPRB-32 have slender grains; UPRB-33 and 8 have short, bold grains. UPRB-31 is also resistant to cold temperature and to bacterial blight; it is being used as a donor parent. All the resistant and moderately resistant collections need to be tested against other stresses.

Varietal reaction to brown spot and narrow leaf spot under natural infection

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Two fungus diseases – brown spot, caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Hann, and narrow leaf spot, caused by *Cercospora oryzae* Miyake – were observed in the northeastern, central, and southern ricegrowing areas of Thailand. Chantharasnit and Aroonskul reported that RD1, RD2, and RD3 were resistant to brown spot under glasshouse conditions and artificial inoculation. Many multiple-resistant lines from the cross BKN 6517-63-4-3/RD9 recently exhibited high susceptibility to brown spot at the heading stage. We suspect that brown spot will become a major disease in the future. Therefore, we tested many breeding lines in the seedling stage for reaction to brown spot and narrow leaf spot under natural infection.

We tested 464 breeding lines from the intrastation and interstation yield trials in the 1975 wet season at the seedling stage under natural infection at the Kuan Gut Rice Experiment Station and the Ubolrajthani Rice Experiment Station. RD1 and Khao Dawk Mali 105 were

used as resistant and susceptible checks, respectively. The test rows were surrounded by two rows of Hang Yi 71 to keep high moisture among the plants. No fertilizer or other chemicals were applied. The reactions of rice plants to brown spot and to narrow leaf spot,

Varieties and lines found to be resistant to brown spot and narrow brown leaf spot.

Designation	Cross	Resistance rating ^a	
		Brown spot	Narrow leaf spot
SPT 6606-100	LT82/Sigadis	R	MR
UBN 6721-5-39-3(1)	IR262A/NSPT	MR	MR
BKN 6721-11-8-4-1	IR262A/NSPT ²	R	MR
KKN 6721-5-7-4	IR262A/NSPT ²	R	MR
SPT 66064-2-1-1	LT82/Sigadis	R	MR
SPT 6606-6-1-1-1	LT82/Sigadis	MR	MR
SPT 6606-36-1-1-1	LT82/Sigadis	MR	MR
SPT 6012-97	GR201/LY34	MR	MR
KDML'65 G ₄ U-4-351	Irr. KDML 105	MR	MR
KDML'65 G ₄ U-4-522	Irr. KDML 105	R	MR
KDML'65 G ₁ U-45	Irr. KDML 105	MR	MR
SKN 24	KDML 105/F16216	MR	R
SKN 48	KDML 105/F16216	MR	MR
SKN 15	KDML 105/F16216	MR	MR
SKN 49	KDML 105/F16216	MR	MR
SPT'58-37-389	DML 70 ² /Chinese 345	MR	MR
SPT'58-37-400	DML 70 ² /Chinese 345	MR	MR
SPT 6207-297	Pin Gaew Bow 27/JL 11	R	R
BKN 323-17	KTH 17/Ramadja	MR	MR
492-2-204	Khao Gaew	MR	MR
KTH'65-G ₂ U-31	Irr. KTH 17	MR	MR
KTH'65-G ₁ U-67	Irr. KTH 17	MR	R
SPRC'70-11-32	Leuang Hawm	MR	MR
SPRC'70-12-45	Khao Pra Juab	MR	MR
SPT 6838-2-1-1	SPT 6624-67/NSPT	MR	MR
SPT 6838-76-2-2-1	SPT 6624-67/NSPT	MR	MR
SPT 6838-87-2-1-4	SPT 662467/NSPT	MR	MR
SPT 6838-96-1-1-1	SPT 662467/NSPT	MR	MR
SPT 6838-125-1-1-2	SPT 6624-67/NSPT	MR	R
SPT 6838-94-1-1-4	SPT 6624-67/NSPT	MR	MR
SPT 6838-86-2-2-1	SPT 662467/NSPT	MR	R
BKN 7130-511	Short Sigadis/KPM 148	MR	MR
SPT 6840-10-2-2-4	NSPT/SPT 6624-67	MR	MR
SPT 6840-80-2-1-2	NSPT/SPT 6624-67	MR	R
SPT 6840-82-2-1-1	NSPT/SPT 6624-67	MR	R
SPT 6840-82-2-1-3	NSPT/SPT 6624-67	MR	MR
SPT 6840-51-2-2-1	NSPT/SPT 662467	MR	MR
	NPY 70	MR	MR
	NSPT	MR	MR

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant.